

Ayurvedic Management of Dermatomyositis: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Dermatomyositis is an inflammatory disease marked by muscle weakness and a distinctive skin rash. The rash can be itchy and painful, is often the first sign of dermatomyositis. The muscle weakness tends to gradually worsen. It is a type of myopathy. We find detail about myopathy but there is detail description of dermatomyositis not only in ayurvedic text but also in modern text but according to symptomatology we can describe it as "Maanspeshishosh." In *AyurvedaPanchkarma* therapy like "*ShashtikshaliPindaSwedan*" and *Basti Chikitsa* is very effective in this. As well as some medications which are *Rasa Yogalike Kumar Kalyan Rasa*, *VatagajankushRasa* and other *VataShamak* and *Balya* medicines etc look beneficial for this disease.

Keywords: Dermatomyositis, Myopathy, *Maanspeshishosh*, *ShashtikshaliPindaSwedan*, *Basti chikitsa*.

INTRODUCTION

Dermatomyositis is one of the type of myopathy. Myopathy is a muscle disease unrelated to any disorder of innervations or neuromuscular junction. Dermatomyositis is a type of inflammatory myopathy which is a type of acquired myopathy. It is an uncommon inflammatory disease marked by muscle weakness and a distinctive skin rash. This can affect adults and children. In children appears between 5 to 15 yrs of age. In adults, occurs from the late 40s to early 60s. The actual cause is unknown but the disease has much common with autoimmune disorder in which your immune

system mistakenly attacks your body tissues. Small blood vessels in muscular tissue are particularly affected in dermatomyositis. Most common symptoms are dusky red rashes most commonly on face, eyelids, knuckles, elbow knees, chest and back, and muscle weakness which affect both the rt. and lt. side of body. In *Ayurveda* there is no description of muscular dystrophy but on the basis of symptoms we can compare it with "*Manspeshishosh*" and planned the treatment according to it.

CASE PRESENTATION

An 8 yrs old Hindu girl patient residing Udaipur presented to the OPD of *Kayachikitsa Govt. Ayurvedic* hospital and research centre, Udaipur on 18/10/19 (OPD No. 11240) with complain of proximal muscle weakness, muscle stiffness, unable to sit, patient can't bent her legs and left hand also, pain in whole body, red patches on face specially around eyes and nose, nodules on both shoulders and fingers also, muscle wasting with poor appetite. Before 4 years suddenly patient felt weakness in her body, she can't stand up herself after sitting, muscle wasting also found. Patient went for some investigation like some blood tests, x-ray both knee joints, USG left shoulder joint etc. on the basis of all symptoms patient diagnosed dermatomyositis. She took treatment for 6 to 7 months and got relief also but during medication she developed stiffness in her feet, can't bent her legs, stiffness in whole joints, boils on

interphalangeal joints. Then patient came here with all above symptoms. On physical examination vitals are normal. When patient

visited allopathy hospital, she is suggested for some blood investigations, X-ray, USG etc.

Table no. 1 Showing examinations and findings.

Examination	Findings
USG left shoulder joint	*Multiple foci of calcifications seen involving chest wall muscles predominantly involving serrata anterior muscle and biceps brachii. *Subcutaneous calcification seen at the tip of left shoulder. *Surrounding subcutaneous tissue edema seen.
X-ray bilateral knee joints AP& LATERAL view	*Multiple foci of soft tissue calcification seen around lower end of bilateral femori. *Subcutaneous calcification focus in right popliteal region.
Chest PA view-	Multiple soft tissue calcification foci seen involving bilateral chest wall and left upper arm predominantly around left shoulder joint superimposing left upper limb zones. Subcutaneous calcification focus at the tip of the left shoulder. Due to calcification patient can't move her leg and right hand.

TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT

In *Ayurveda* there is no description of dermatomyositis but on the basis of symptoms we planned a line of treatment for the patient. When patient visited first time in the hospital, she is suggested to admit in hospital for 10 days and treated with some *Panchakarma* therapies and medication also, after 10 days patient show remarkable improvement. Follow up given in 10 – 10 days.

Table No. 2 Showing given treatment to the patient and follow up.

Date	S.No.	Given treatment	Anupana
18/10/19	1.	<i>Sashdikshali Pinda Sweda</i> <i>Matra Basti with Saindhvadi Tail</i> <i>Vata Gajankush Rasa</i> 1BD <i>Dashmularishta</i> – 10ml <i>Arvindasava</i> - 10ml BD	Luke warm water
30/10/19	2.	<i>Kumarkalyan rasa</i> – 100mg <i>Vatagajankush rasa</i> – 125mg <i>Punarnavamandoor</i> – 250 mg <i>Sitopaladichurna</i> – 2 gm BD <i>Dashmularishta</i> - 10 ml <i>Arvindasava</i> - 10ml BD <i>BalaAshwagandhadi Tail + Saindhvadi Tail</i> <i>(SthanikAbhyangand Swedan)</i>	<i>Madhu</i> Water
13/11/19	3.	Repeated same t/t	

This treatment continued for few months. In this preparation *Kumar Kalyaan Rasais* best *Rasayan* as well as *Yogvahi* property. It is very effective in malnutrition and *VataVikarain* children. *VataGajankush Rasais* beneficial in *Vataand KaphaDoshas*. It is used in paralysis, arthritis, all cases of stiffness and cramps, ankle pain, promote strength of bones and joints. It acts as an excellent anti inflammatory and analgesic medicine.

Punarnava Mandoor works as anti-inflammatory, anti oxidant and digestive stimulant. It heals your skin and increase blood level.

Sitopaladi Churna is a beneficial in a variety of diseases relating to respiratory, digestive and immune system. It is

antiinflammatory, immunomodulatory, antacid, appetizer and antioxidant. It is helpful in tuberculosis, rickets, debility, lack of physical strength and loss of appetite.

Dashmoolarishta is useful in *Dhatukshaya, Aruchi, VataVyadhi, Agnimandhya* and *Kamala*. It is used in *Vata* and *KaphaDoshas*. It is anti inflammatory, anti arthritic, digestive stimulant, mild natural analgesic, muscle relaxant, anti stress and anti depressant etc.

Arvindasava is mainly pacifies *Vataand* also works to balance *Pitta* and *Kapha Doshas*. It is used in children to improve digestion, body weight and strength. It has many nutritional ingredient by which it can be use in delayed milestone, rickets, weakness and low bone density etc.

Shastikshali Pinda Swedan is used to provide nutrition, strength of the body tissues, including the muscles, bones and soft tissues. It energizes and rejuvenates the body, prevents muscle wasting.

Basti Chikitsais known as half of *Chikitsain Ayurveda*. *Matra Basti* is a type of *Anvasana Basti* and least dose of *Snehpana*. It is said that *Matra Basti* is “*Sarva Kala Niratyayam*” it means there is no complication of *Matra Basti* which can be administered any time and any condition.

DISCUSSION

Dermatomyositis is a *Kshayaj Vyadhi* in which *Shosh* of *Maanspeshi* found. In present case patient advised *Shastikshalika Pinda Swedan* and *Matra Basti*. *Shastikshali* contains *Masha*, *Shali*, *BalaBeeja*, *Dashmool Kashaya* and milk also. All these ingredients have *Balya* and *Poshana* property. *MatraBasti* is *balya*, *Bringhana* and *VataRoga Shamaka* and for *Maanspeshishoshabalya Chikitsa* is best line of treatment. In this preparation oral medicines which given to the patient, *Kumarkalyana Rasa* have *Swarna*, *Mukta*, *loha* and *Abhrakabhasma*, all type of *Bhasmas* have anti inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, antacids, cardioprotective properties. *lohabhasma* useful in iron deficiency, Anemia, muscle weakness and *Kapha* disorders. *Vata Gajankusha Rasa* has *Kajjali* and *Trikatu* etc which have *Deepan Pachana* quality. In *Punarnava Mandoor Trikatu*, *Amalaki*, *Haritaki* has *Rasayana* property, *Vidanga* is antifungal and antibacterial and used to improve skin pigmentation, weakness and fatigue and in this disease skin problem and weakness also found. The actual cause of dermatomyositis is unknown but if we go to the symptomatology all these medicines are helpful in dermatomyositis or *Maanspeshishosha* because in condition of

Shosha balya and *bringhaniya* medicines are the 1st line of treatment.

CONCLUSION

Result of this study shows that *Ayurveda* have the capability to improve these type of myopathies. There is no correlation but according to symptomatology *Balya*, *Bringhaniya*, *Deepan*, *Paachan Aushadhi* and *Panchakarma therapies* provided better results in management of dermatomyositis or *Maanspeshishosha*. Specially *Basti Chikita* and *Swedana* plays an important role to cure these type of diseases. In this case we get remarkable improvement in subjective parameters.

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